

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Oryza minuta is not endemic to the Philippines

D. A. Vaughan, *International Rice Germplasm Center, IRRI*; and G. Gorogo, *Department of Primary Industry, Port Moresby, Papua New Guinea*

The diploid species *Oryza officinalis* and tetraploid species *O. minuta* have been confused in the literature. The two species, however, can be clearly distinguished on the basis of spikelet dimension, panicle structure, and habit.

Herbarium studies show *O. minuta* had previously been found only in the Philippines. *O. officinalis* is widely distributed from India to Papua New Guinea. On the islands of the Malay archipelago, it has been collected in Sabah, Sarawak, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Sumatra, Java, Halmahera, Bacan Island, and Western Province of Papua New Guinea.

We report finding several populations of *O. minuta* (see figure) around Wasua village (08:20S latitude, 142:50E longitude) in Western Province, Papua New Guinea. The stoloniferous species was growing, either in shade or partial sunlight, beside a small creek in sago swamps. We did not find *O. officinalis* in the area, but did collect it along the south coast of Western Province.

Spikelets of *O. minuta* populations in the Philippines are thicker than those of populations collected in Papua New Guinea (see table). □

Distribution of *Oryza minuta* (▼).

Spikelet dimensions of *Oryza minuta*.

Collection no.	Site	Spikelet dimension ^a (mm)		
		Length	Width	Thickness
<i>Philippines</i>				
P90-1	Luzon	4.7	1.8	1.4
P90-6	Samar	4.5	1.8	1.3
P90-17	Leyte	4.8	1.9	1.2
P90-19	Southern Leyte	4.7	1.8	1.4
<i>Papua New Guinea</i>				
91PNG-17	Western Province	4.5	1.9	0.9
91PNG-18	Western Province	4.2	1.9	0.9
91PNG-19	Western Province	4.5	2.0	1.0
91PNG-20	Western Province	4.7	2.0	1.0

^aMean of 10 measurements per population.

Breeding methods

Identification of promising CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines for developing Philippine rice hybrids

R. J. Lara, I. A. dela Cruz, and M. S. F. Ablaza, *Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice)*, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija; and S. S. Virmani, *IRRI*

Five cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines obtained from IRRI were evaluated at three locations in the Philippines for pollen sterility, spikelet fertility of bagged panicles, field reaction to rice tungro virus, and days to 50% flowering.

Stable CMS lines were V20 A and IR46830 A (both with CMS-WA cytoplasm), and IR54755 A (CMS-ARC cytoplasm). CMS lines IR58025 A and

IR62829 A were nearly stable for male sterility (Table 1).

IR54755 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A showed slight to no infection with tungro viruses. Outcrossing potential of IR62829 A, IR58025 A, and V20 A was acceptable. CMS lines flowered at 81-102 d at IRRI, but at 102-116 d at Banaue (high altitude, lower temperature). IR58025 A and IR62829 A

Table 1. Behavior of some CMS lines at 3 locations in the Philippines.

CMS line	Location	Pollen sterility ^a	Seed setting (%) of bagged panicles	Reaction to RTV ^b	Outcrossing potential ^c	Days to 50% flowering
V20 A	IRRI	CS	0	S	3	83
	Banaue	CS	0	R		102
	San Mateo	CS	0	I		81
IR46830 A	IRRI	CS	0	I	9	86
	Banaue	CS	0			108
	San Mateo	CS	0	I		89
IR54755 A	IRRI	CS	0	R	9	81
	Banaue	CS	0	R		108
	San Mateo	CS	0	R		88
IR58025 A	IRRI	CS	0	I	3	102
	Banaue	CS	0	R		116
	San Mateo	S	0.33	R		90
IR62829 A	IRRI	CS	0	I	1	85
	Banaue	PS	2.20	R		105
	San Mateo	S	0.05	R		84

^a CS = completely sterile (0% fertility), S = sterile (1.10% fertility), PS = partially sterile (11.30% fertility), ^b RTV = rice tungro viruses. R = no infection, I = slight infection, S = severe infection. ^c Outcrossing potential on 1–9 scale: 1 = high and 9 = low.

Table 2. Maintainer and restorer lines identified at Philippine Rice Research Institute, 1990-91 dry seasons.

Cultivar	Tester CMS line	Backcrosses (no.)
<i>Maintainers</i>		
BPI 30-2	IR62829 A	3
MRC22387-859	V20 A	3
BPI 121-407	IR62829 A	2
IR5537-32-D	IR62829 A	1
IR55548-05	IR62829 A	1
IR57893-26	IR62829 A	1
	IR58025 A	
IR60076-04	IR62829 A	1
IR60080-45	IR62829 A	1
IR57934-02	IR54755 A	1
IR60077-09	IR54755 A	1
IR60080-35	IR54755 A	1
IR60080-41	IR54755 A	1
IR55543-51-B	IR58025 A	1
Cavitena	IR58025 A	1
<i>Restorers</i>		
BPI Ri 10	IR62829 A	–
MRC11055-432-23	IR62829 A	–
MRC18186-611	IR62829 A	–
MRC18624-1466	IR62829 A	–
MRC22367-807	IR62829 A	–
Mantika Banguin	IR62829 A	–
PR21209-389-5	IR62829 A	–
RP1057-393-1	IR62829 A	–
OR141-99	IR62829 A	–
IR66	IR62829 A	–
IR3380-60-1-2-2	IR62829 A	–
IR31432-9-3-2	IR62829 A	–
BR11-461-1	IR62829 A	–
BR425-189-1-6-2-1-2	IR62829 A	–
BR316-15-4-4-1	IR62829 A	–
BR11	IR62829 A	–
IR60080-27	IR62829 A	–
PR23342-5	IR62829 A	–

were selected to develop heterotic rice hybrids.

We made 251 testcrosses using elite lines, IR62829 A, and IR58025 A to identify maintainers and restorers. Pollen sterility was 98–100% in testcross F₁s. This indicates that the male parent is a maintainer that can be converted into a CMS line by recurrent backcrossing.

Testcross F₁s showed normal seed setting (more than 75%), indicating that the elite line is a restorer and can be used as a male parent in developing heterotic rice hybrids. We identified 14 maintainer and 18 restorer lines (Table 2).

Maintainer lines have been backcrossed 1–3 times to convert them into CMS lines. Restorers are being purified by re-test crossing single plants before use in developing experimental rice hybrids for yield testing. □

Low light-tolerant restorers in hybrid rice breeding

K. S. Murty and S. K. Dey, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Low light during reproductive and ripening phases can critically constrain rice productivity during wet season.

We studied the low-light adaptability of 19 IRRI purified restorers during dry season. Wooden screens artificially shaded plants (50% normal light) from 35 d after planting to harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. The

Effect of 50% shade from 35 d to harvest on total dry matter (TDM) and yield of restorers. 1990 dry season.

Restorer	TDM (g/m ²)		Reduction (%)	Yield (g/m ²)		Reduction (%)
	Light	Shade		Light	Shade	
IR36	872	433	51.3	405	170	58.0
IR46	866	360	58.4	440	96	78.2
IR50	775	500	35.5	399	200	49.9
IR54	983	528	46.3	406	193	52.5
IR58	1190	350	70.6	450	118	73.8
IR64	896	479	46.5	446	204	54.3
Milyang 54	654	473	27.7	302	186	38.4
ARC1 1353	888	542	39.0	373	173	53.6
IR4422-480-2-3-3	974	599	38.5	338	209	38.2
IR9761-19-1	625	414	33.8	305	165	46.0
IR13419-113-1	993	414	58.3	483	147	69.6
IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	713	305	57.2	365	118	67.7
IR19058-107-1	930	577	38.0	413	232	43.8
IR19392-211-1	937	425	54.6	466	181	61.2
IR21916-128-2-2-3	1029	436	57.6	493	153	69.0
IR25912-63-2-2	856	466	45.6	435	137	68.5
IR27315-145-1-3	1013	460	54.6	318	133	58.2
IR28178-70-2-3	719	537	25.3	291	179	38.5
IR29723-143-3-2-1	854	436	48.9	424	127	70.0
Annapurna (check)	759	391	48.5	326	126	61.3
Jaya (check)	978	524	46.4	401	230	42.6
Mean	881	459	46.8	394	165	56.8
LSD (0.05)						
Treatments (T)				21		
Variety (V)				55		
V at same T				77		
T for same V				89		